

TECHNOLOGY - AIDED MODELS FOR TRACING & TRACKING COVID-19 AND POTENTIAL DATA COLLECTION MODES

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In collaboration with

WORKING PAPER SERIES

ISSUE - 01 | JANUARY - 2021

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>Abstract</i>	01
1. Introduction	01
2. Digital Technology in pandemic management	02
2.1 - Digital tools used for tracing and tracking	02
3. Tracking Covid-19	03
4. Contact Tracing for Covid-19	05
4.1 - Manual Contact Tracing	06
4.2 - Digital Contact Tracing	06
5. Modes of Data Collection and Storage	09
5.1 - Knowledge of Infectious Diseases: Some Trends	10
6. Ethical, Privacy and Legal Considerations	11
7. Aarogya Setu and India's Contact tracing efforts	13
7.1 - Issues that Affected its Uptake	14
8. Analysis of tracing and testing policy across different countries	15
8.1 - India	16
8.1.1 - How the States Fared in Contact Tracing	21
8.2 - Singapore	23
8.3 - Vietnam	25
8.4 - Thailand	26
8.5 - South Korea	27
8.6 - United Kingdom	29
8.7 - United States	30
8.8 - Comparison of Digital Contact Tracing Models	31
9. Principles for a Technology-aided model for tracing and tracking Covid-19 in India	34
9.1 - Policy Considerations	34
9.2 - Combination of manual and digital contact tracing interventions	34
10. Way Forward: Role of IoT, Big Data Analytics, AI and Blockchain Technology	37
11. Vaccine Delivery - The Priority List	38
<i>References</i>	39

ABSTRACT

Digital tracking and tracing tools for Covid-19 would enable the creation of databases that could then be used to prioritise the vaccination plan and ensure that the most vulnerable are inoculated first and that the entire population is covered in quick time. This paper seeks to lay out the principles for possible technology-aided models to do effective tracing and tracking, and potential data collection modes on testing and tracing that can support the national vaccination plan for Covid-19. The premise is that each of these steps is critical in first controlling and then arresting the spread of the COVID 19 virus.

How can technology aid in tracing and tracking without being intrusive in private lives through apps and digital tools? What have been the points of resistance that have obstructed Arogya Setu's faster adoption in the country? What are the principles of a prudent common digital tracking system that can help us trace potential virus carriers in real-time and save us from infection transmission without compromising individual privacy, and safety? While addressing these issues, the paper also seeks to look into how data from tracing could be collated so as to strengthen Covid-19 documentation in general and specifically aid the vaccination plan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Measures for contact tracing and disease tracking are critical, especially in the early stages of disease outbreak, to isolate those infected and contain onward transmission. Besides interrupting the chain of transmission by alerting and isolating those who may have contracted the disease, data collected from tracing and tracking measures can help forecast future outbreaks. Such interventions also enable the creation of digital databases that could be used to prioritise the vaccination plan and ensure that the most vulnerable are inoculated first. Tracing and tracking measures are, however, ineffective in the absence of widespread testing. This is why access to testing becomes important as well.

In the current stage of the Covid-19 pandemic in India, widespread testing, tracing and tracking become crucial to identify vulnerable groups, understand how the disease is spreading, and develop effective vaccination plans and disease control strategies. However, these measures have faltered at various levels despite large expenditures, serious political will and the extensive use of available technology.

The lessons we learn from Vietnam and Thailand, both exemplars in handling a potentially explosive crisis, are that tracking potential carriers and tracing contacts have been crucial in controlling the epidemic. It is then that people were encouraged to stay away from crowds, wear masks and maintain physical distances. This combination ensured that both these countries remained largely protected. The WHO chief pointed out the various ways in which Thailand was able to control the spread despite an exceedingly early case and a crowded capital city.

2. DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN PANDEMIC MANAGEMENT

The Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the adoption of digital technologies to respond to public health crises and clinical problems in nations around the world. Digital technologies are increasingly being looked at as solutions that can aid epidemiological surveillance, early and timely detection, interruption of disease transmission in communities, and communication of health information to the public (Budd et al., 2020).

WHO's International Health Regulations call on member states to put in place public health surveillance systems that can provide data crucial for their national pandemic response plans. Public health experts and researchers, too, widely acknowledge the benefits of collecting and analysing data from a range of digital sources such as telephone towers, mobile phone apps, Bluetooth connections, surveillance video, social media feeds, smart thermometers, credit card records, wearables, and several other devices (Gasser, Ienca, Scheibner, Sleigh and Vayena, 2020). However, such technology requires access to a digital device in most cases. Challenges also remain in ensuring transparency and accountability, and safeguarding data and privacy rights.

2.1 Digital tools used for tracing and tracking

- **Tracking disease** activity in real time using data dashboards, migration maps, machine learning, real-time data from smartphones and wearable technology. Such tools allow visual depiction of spread, directs border restrictions, guides resource allocation, and informs forecasts.
- **Contact tracing** tools identify and trace individuals who might have come into contact with an infected person. They also aid in tracking the viral spread. Such tools use global positioning systems, mobile phone applications, and real-time monitoring of mobile devices and wearable technology, among others.

Examples of dashboards and web-based platforms used to track and trace Covid-19:

1. Johns Hopkins COVID-19 dashboard to track cases globally
2. Canadian health company BlueDot's predictions of infectious disease outbreaks based on traditional and non-traditional sources such as flight information, and CDC and WHO reports and statistics
3. Digital contact tracing smartphone applications in use in countries such as India, South Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, Switzerland
4. Smartwatch application in Germany that collects vital information to screen for signs of Covid-19
5. HealthMap uses AI and data mining to generate real-time information on the outbreak

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY FOR PANDEMIC MANAGEMENT

Uses:

- Epidemiological surveillance
- Early and timely detection
- Interruption of chain of disease transmission
- Communication of healthcare information to public

Classified under four main functional categories:

- 1) Proximity and contact tracing: Gauges spatial proximity between users and tracks their interactions. E.g. TraceTogether (Singapore).
- 2) Syndromic surveillance: Symptom monitoring, and collection and analysis of reported health data. E.g. CoronaMadrid (Spain).
- 3) Quarantine compliance: Ensures compliance of suspected patients with quarantine regulations by monitoring them real-time. E.g. Electronic Fence (Taiwan).
- 4) Flow modelling: Mobility reports that quantify and track people's movements in specified regions, thereby gauging the effectiveness of public health measures already taken. E.g. Google's Community Mobility Reports.

Source: (Gasser, Ienca, Scheibner, Sleigh and Vayena, 2020).

3. TRACKING COVID-19

Tracking interventions are primarily used to track disease activity in real-time and understand how the infection is spreading in various regions. Traditional disease surveillance mechanisms rely on data gathered from healthcare facilities and syndromic surveillance networks. However, these sources risk missing out on cases that go undetected and those that do not seek healthcare. Digital epidemiological surveillance tools collect data from a range of digital sources; including social media, online news sites and web searches, to fill this gap.

Online symptom reporting systems for Covid-19, as used in the UK and Singapore, can also go a long way in rapid case identification and triaging. Challenges, however, exist in ensuring quality of data captured in the absence of standards and consistency in data collection. This also affects interoperability of systems across nations for wider coordination on Covid-19 response (Budd et al., 2020)

Chinese authorities used tools such as migration maps, which depend on mobile phone application, mobile payment applications and social media to track in real-time people who had visited the Wuhan market, where the pandemic first broke out (Whitelaw, Mamas, Topol, and Van Spall, 2020). Sweden's health workers record Covid-19 data on case volumes, number of ventilator beds in use, staffing and the like on an online platform in real time. This is shared nationwide with health authorities for better allocation of resources.

TRACKING TOOLS & TECHNOLOGY IN USE

- Web-based epidemic intelligence tools such as ProMED-mail, GPHIN, HealthMap and EIOS use natural language processing and machine learning to provide epidemiological insights.
- WHO's platform EPI-BRAIN collates diverse datasets, including environmental and meteorological data for infectious-disease emergency preparedness and response.
- The UK's automatic syndromic surveillance system filters the National Health System digital records for cases with respiratory illness to track Covid-19 cases.
- Crowdsourcing systems like InfluenzaNet gather information on symptoms and compliance with physical distancing measures from volunteers in different European countries using regular surveys. Symptom reporting systems like COVID Near You use survey apps and websites
- Data dashboards that use data extraction and visualisation tools are updated real-time to help in public communication as well as informing response decisions.

MOBILITY REPORTS

Mobility data with privacy-preserving aggregation has been used to generate reports that quantify and track people's movements in specified regions. Mobility reports help evaluate the effectiveness of physical distancing rules and lockdowns in place. Such data is collected by smartphones via GPS, cellular network and Wi-Fi. They also help track population flows, and identify potential spots for fresh outbreaks. Monitoring of physical distancing measures become crucial in predicting future health system demands and in assessing the lifting of restrictions. Daily aggregated travel data from Baidu is used to measure effectiveness of travel curbs in China. Google also releases weekly Community Mobility Reports with sub-national granularity that are publicly available. (Budd et al., 2020)

4. CONTACT TRACING FOR COVID-19

Contact tracing refers to a variety of methods used to identify, notify and assess those who may have come in close proximity with a person who has tested positive for a certain infection. Such measures are widely used to inform, isolate and ensure treatment of those who may have been exposed to a disease. It has been used to break the chain of transmission in infectious diseases such as tuberculosis, SARS, Ebola and MERS. (Hart et al., 2020). Contact tracing can be carried out manually (e.g. door-to-door surveillance by health workers), digitally (using proximity tracking applications) or as a hybrid of both.

3 STEPS OF CONTACT TRACING

Contact tracing involves three basic steps:

CONTACT IDENTIFICATION → **CONTACT LISTING** → **CONTACT FOLLOW-UP**

Source: WHO (2017)

Studies have shown that outside of pharmaceutical interventions, moderate physical distancing measures and widespread testing, when combined with self-isolation and contact tracing, could significantly help in breaking the chain of transmission of the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). A modelling study on the effectiveness of isolation, testing, contact tracing, and physical distancing on reducing transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in different settings shows that a combination of isolation and contact tracing strategies was more effective than mass testing or self-isolation alone (Kucharski et al., 2020). Other studies have shown that optimised contact tracing can be effective with high coverage of testing and tracing, and if it is carried out without much delay (Kretzschmar et al., 2020).

A survey of attitudes to contact-tracing across 19 countries found nearly three-quarters of respondents expressed willingness to provide contact information. However, these rates varied largely. While in Vietnam, only 4% of participants said they would not disclose the details, this proportion was 25% in France. The number of contacts identified for each Covid-19 case also varies greatly, from an average of 17 per case in Taiwan to 2 in the United Kingdom and less than one in parts of the United States (Lewis, 2020).

4.1 Manual Contact Tracing

Contact tracing can be carried out manually with the help of trained health workers who will identify and interview a person who has tested positive and alert those who have come in contact with them. This process is repeated to narrow down on secondary contacts, who are also isolated and monitored for symptoms. Manual contact tracing data can be largely unreliable at times as it depends on human memory. It also requires time and trained human resources. This makes it infeasible to continue manual contact tracing efforts in earnest once the disease enters the community transmission phase. Moreover, it has proven ineffective in controlling a highly infectious virus such as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) that has a long incubation period.

THE CASE OF KERALA

Manual contact-tracing and surveillance measures are not sustainable, as is evident from the situation in Kerala. Over 17,000 non-medical volunteers (Government of Kerala, 2020) had enlisted themselves for physical contact-tracing, surveillance and healthcare provision at first-line treatment centres during the onset of the pandemic which helped keep the pandemic in check then. However, fatigue soon set in among frontline health workers, volunteers, and the public, leading to a severe spike in new cases after markets reopened during the festival of Onam, and international and domestic travel resumed.

4.2 Digital Contact Tracing

Digital contact tracing tools use global positioning systems, mobile phone applications, and real-time monitoring of mobile devices and wearable technology for patient identification, digital health records, and proximity tracking. Such tools aid prioritised testing of individuals who are known to have come in contact with an infected person in a timely manner. They also rely less on manpower. While automated contact tracing tools could be effective in interrupting the chain of transmission with sufficient uptake, data privacy issues and the risk of marginalising underserved communities must be considered (Braithwaite, Callender, Bullock and Aldridge, 2020). Since such tools have not been used at this scale for pandemic responses before, it is essential they are evaluated for accuracy and effectiveness.

Several proximity tracking apps (O'Neill, Ryan-Mosley and Johnson, 2020), including India's Aarogya Setu, were launched to facilitate contact-tracing of infected persons. These applications gauge signal strength to determine whether two smartphones/devices have come in close contact with each other. Such apps, however, could only be used to aid surveillance efforts and not

supplant physical tracing and tracking measures that must be carried out by the health authorities. These applications are limited in the range of scenarios they can capture where a person is possibly exposed to the virus. They are, at best, effective in informing a person of their risk of contracting the virus due to contact and the further steps they can take to avoid onward transmission (WHO, 2020). They can also be used to provide data that will aid decisions taken by public health authorities to respond to the pandemic. In the case of cell phone applications for proximity tracing, it is estimated that at least 50% of the population should have it installed for it to be effective. Moreover, such tracing also tends to miss out on children who do not have their own devices, yet are known to play a big role in transmitting the virus in communities (Haart, Siddhart et al., 2020).

PROS AND CONS OF DIGITAL CONTACT TRACING TECHNOLOGY:

Advantages

- 1) Cost and time-effective.
- 2) Aids prioritised testing of individuals who are known to have come in contact with an infected person.
- 3) Relies less on manpower, can be scaled.
- 4) Allows for real-time tracing of individuals and disease transmission patterns.

Disadvantages:

- 1) Technical limitations in capturing all scenarios under which a person can contract the disease. It also misses out on tracing children.
- 2) Cannot supplant manual contact tracing efforts due to socio-economic inequalities that affect uptake of such digital tools.
- 3) Challenges w.r.t. interoperability and standardisation of data collected.
- 4) Security risks and privacy issues.

COLLECTION OF LOCATION DATA FOR CONTACT TRACING

Contact-tracing apps collect location data using:

- 1) Global Positioning System (GPS) and location-based
 - Detects everyone at the same GPS coordinates, including different people in the same building.
 - Inaccurate when used in multi-storey buildings or mass underground transit systems.
 - Uses and stores location histories that are more vulnerable to de-anonymisation.

2) Bluetooth

- Will detect only those within a certain 3D radius
 - Works reliably underground, indoors, and in motion
 - Accuracy advantage over GPS for in-person contacts.
 - Privacy advantage over GPS because the only information involved is contact tokens, which can be cryptographically secured in a way that is less vulnerable to de-anonymisation
 - Less accurate to determine surface transmission and need for decontamination.
- 3) Several applications also use a combination of Bluetooth, GPS, Wifi and cellular network data.

COMBINATION APPROACH

It is pertinent here to note that 46.4% of the world lacked internet access in the beginning of 2020, as per data put out by the International Telecommunications Union. Physical interventions can augment digital contact tracing efforts in areas with low digital penetration, though various studies estimate that at least 40% penetration is required for such applications to be effective (Gasser et al, 2020).

By using a combination of both digital and physical measures, a large range of health and demographic data can be captured. Phone location data can also be used to augment one's own memory of whom they have been in contact with during in-person contact-tracing interviews. Studies have also shown that a system that combines both manual and digital tracing tools generates better contact identification data compared with that collected using manual contact tracing.

5. MODES OF DATA COLLECTION AND STORAGE

Contact tracing data gathered by digital tools can be collected and stored in a centralised or decentralised manner. This difference has been at the centre of a failed European Union bid to align their contact tracing measures (Grimwood-Taylor, 2020). On the one side of the debate is an umbrella group of academics and business stakeholders pushing for PEPP-PT (Pan-European Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing) protocol that uses a centralised system. On the other side is another consortium of academics and technology firms calling for DP3T, a decentralised approach on privacy-preserved proximity tracking. Both use Bluetooth technology for proximity tracking. Tech giants like Google and Apple have also partnered to build an API-based interface that is based on a DP3T-based system (Criddle & Kelion, 2020).

Of the 42 countries that have revealed its policy on centralisation or decentralisation of storage of data captured through contact tracing tools, 17 have chosen the former approach. This group has seen larger uptake of its apps as well (Agrawal, 2020).

Tracing protocol that can help mitigate privacy risks during digital contact tracing include:

1. **Peer-to-peer data protocol through Bluetooth:** All or most data is stored on the user's device. Anonymised data is sent to a central server with secure keys.
2. **Location-based protocol through GPS:** All personal data is stored on the user's device. Aggregated data is sent to a central server securely through encryption, only if required (Hart, Siddart et al.)

GOOGLE APPLE API IN INDIA

Though Google and Apple collaborated to develop technology for contact-tracing, it is currently unavailable in India as the Aarogya Setu app requires access to users' movement and GPS location data for contact-tracing. On the other hand, the API (application programming interface) developed by Google and Apple denies public health applications access to users' location. It exchanges anonymised codes with nearby phones over Bluetooth connection to identify potential exposure. The ID changes periodically to ensure better privacy for individual users.

5.1 Knowledge of Infectious Diseases: Some Trends

Self-awareness, contact tracing and widespread testing go hand-in-hand. The knowledge of HIV-AIDS among adults in various states in India is used here to assess trends that may follow in the case of another infectious disease such as Covid-19.

Knowledge of HIV-AIDS among adults

A more significant proportion of men than women had a comprehensive knowledge of HIV-AIDS. A higher percentage of men in urban areas possessed comprehensive knowledge of HIV-AIDS. While in some states such as Goa and Kerala, the urban-rural divide on the knowledge of HIV-AIDS was absent, in others such as Gujarat and WB this divide is extremely wide. In Bihar and Assam, the proportion of the population with knowledge on HIV-AIDS remains low.

Knowledge of HIV-AIDS among adults

Between 2016 and 2020, Goa, Gujarat and Jammu and Kashmir saw a significant increase in the proportion of adults with comprehensive knowledge on HIV-AIDS. Assam saw a marginal improvement from 2015-16. The rest of the states witnessed a decline in this regard. Gujarat and Maharashtra saw an increase in the proportion of women with complete knowledge of HIV-AIDS.

We can, thus, assume some states such as Kerala and Goa will also be front-runners in spreading awareness and hence combating COVID19. In contrast, states like Bihar, West Bengal and Assam will need a considerable period to move past the pandemic fully. The data also points out to the glaring inequalities that persist with regards to gender and urban-rural areas. It is highly likely that the current pandemic will also assume a similar trajectory.

6. ETHICAL, PRIVACY AND LEGAL CONSIDERATIONS

As the Covid-19 virus spread, several governments around the world curbed civil liberties and privacy rights for disease surveillance and containment. Civil society organisations and human rights groups raised concerns over how such measures could easily go down the slippery slope of population surveillance and result in the exclusion of vulnerable communities as well.

The use of highly granular and personalised data carries increased risk of reidentification of individuals or groups. It is, therefore, essential that all digital technology systems in place are proofed against external attacks and other invasions of privacy. With the vast amount of data being gathered, public health agencies and application developers must prevent downstream reidentification through data linkage. Strong legislative protection is also required for this, and to ensure the data captured is not repurposed for commercial interests or state surveillance.

With concerns emerging over the centralised system and GPS tracing, several international frameworks with varying levels of privacy preservation are emerging, including Decentralized Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing, the Pan-European Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing initiative and the joint Google–Apple framework (Budd, J., Miller, B.S., Manning, E.M. et al, 2020).

WHO guidelines for digital proximity tracking technology for Covid-19 tracing

In its interim guidance on ‘Ethical considerations to guide the use of digital proximity tracking technologies for Covid-19 contact tracing’ (WHO, 2020), WHO highlighted the risks of having private companies involved in the collection and analysis of such data, among others. These are some of the basic guidelines highlighted:

1. All measures taken for digital proximity tracing must have a **time limit**, and must be withdrawn as soon as the end of the pandemic is in sight.
2. Digital tools in use must be **evidence-based and tested** by independent bodies for security and data privacy.
3. Data collected must be least-intrusive. Its collection and processing must be **proportionate and provided by law**, and should avoid the physical location tracking of users.
4. Only **minimal data** must be collected and its **use or sale for commercial purposes must be strictly prohibited**.
5. Such apps must be used on a **voluntary basis** where each individual makes a well-informed decision to sign up and report symptoms. They should be allowed to turn off the app or delete it without any consequences whatsoever. Users must be provided with concise and user-friendly information on the app and its operational mechanism.
6. **Transparency and accountability** must be ensured.
7. Collected data must be **secure and encrypted, and anonymised wherever applicable**.
8. Data must be **retained only till the end of the pandemic response**, except for the purposes of research or epidemic planning, subject to appropriate regulation, oversight and informed consent, where required.
9. **Notifications for possible exposure** to an infected person could be sent directly to those in close contact. The latter’s privacy must be ensured during this process.
10. **Independent oversight** of both public agencies and businesses that develop, operate digital proximity tracking applications or use information obtained through them.

7. AAROGYA SETU AND INDIA'S CONTACT TRACING EFFORTS

Several proximity tracking apps, including Aarogya Setu, were launched in India to facilitate contact-tracing of infected persons, especially during the onset of the pandemic (Mihindukulasuriya, 2020). As of December 2020, Aarogya Setu had recorded more than 16 crore installations since its launch in April 2020. Despite being the most-downloaded contact tracing app globally, only less than 12% of the country's total population has used it.

The app uses GPS (Global Positioning System) and Bluetooth to track other Aarogya Setu-enabled phones in close proximity of a user, and alerts them about possible exposure. It can be used to self-report suspected symptoms, and for public messaging on quarantine and isolation guidelines as well. The 'Aarogya Setu Interactive Voice Response System' was also launched to cover those using landlines and feature phones. Data collected from the calls is fed into the app's database.

Contact and GPS data remain on the users' device under normal circumstances and are related to a specific device identification number (DiD). The data is stored in an encrypted server operated and managed by the Government of India. Interactions between users and between a user and the server is carried out only through the DiD.

All contact tracing and location data pertaining to users who have not tested positive are deleted from the devices every 30 days. If a user is 'at risk', data from the GPS and contact data from the past thirty days will be sent to the central server. This data, too, is deleted from the app's server every 45 days, according to information given in the app's privacy policy. The privacy policy states that only aggregated and anonymised data for visualisation is used by the Government of India. All tracing and location data collected for those who have tested positive will be purged from the system 60 days after they have been declared cured. Anonymised, aggregated datasets generated by the personal data of registered users of the app or any reports, heat maps or other visualization created using such datasets can be retained. Medical reports, diagnoses or other information generated by medical professionals in the course of treatment may also be retained.

The captured data is fine-tuned and analysed using a predictive back-end tool called ITIHAS (IT-enabled Integrated Hotspot Analysis System) that also assesses data reported by Indian Council for Medical Research (ICMR). Data collected from physical contact tracing interventions about positive and suspected cases is fed into the app using a real-time API that links the two programmes.

7.1 Issues that Affected its Uptake

Opacity: A certain lack of transparency over the design and development of the app and the private sector's involvement in it has caused a significant trust deficit that affected its uptake. While the app is owned and operated by the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology's National Informatics Centre, external volunteers who helped design it may be associated with companies that have a direct conflict of interest. Following calls for transparency, the government released the client-side code of the app and not the back-end code, as claimed by some experts (Banerje, 2020). It provides little clarity on how data is stored or processed, and further eroded public trust in the app.

Mandatory Use: While several countries around the world launched similar applications for contact tracing, India is the only democracy that has enforced its use by mandating it for travel and work, and other uses. Cities like Noida in Uttar Pradesh brought in strict penalties, including fines and jail terms, for those found outdoors without the app (Shashidhar, 2020). Since the app was introduced through an enforcement-oriented approach, it has failed to guide user behaviour. Coupled with the stigma attached to testing positive, users tend to misreport symptoms during self-assessment to ensure access to work and other public amenities where the app is mandated (Johari, 2020).

Digital Divide: For Aarogya Setu to be successful, at least 50% of the population (Shashidhar, 2020) should be using it. Considering that only 50% of India's population currently has access to the internet and only about 24% of Indians use a smartphone, uptake has remained a major issue. While it may be easier for 50% of those residing in urban areas to use the app, similar penetration in rural areas may not be possible. In the absence of consistent physical contact tracing efforts in all states to supplement the app, its utility in identifying emerging hotspots will remain limited. The usage of Bluetooth and GPS location tracking also drains the smartphone of its battery. Therefore, limited access to electricity and charging points has also been a factor that affected the app's uptake (Joshi and Kak, 2020).

Concerns over privacy:

Data rights activists have raised concerns over privacy of the captured data, and the amount of demographic and personal data that is stored on central servers. Questions have also been raised over the possibility of the app being repurposed after the pandemic ends, especially in the context of the creation of India's National Health Stack under National Digital Health Mission (Johari, 2020). Moreover, in the absence of a Personal Data Protection law, there are no legal safeguards in place against misuse of personal data fed into the app. This also feeds into fears over the captured data being used to target specific groups and communities (Joshi and Kak, 2020).

Efficacy of the App:

The lack of digital literacy has caused widespread underreporting and a large number of false positives as several users are unable to fill out the self-assessment questionnaire correctly. Moreover, the Bluetooth proximity detection feature fails to provide accurate results for possible exposure. As cases peaked, users felt the app was no longer useful in detecting exposure in the absence of accuracy.

NATIONAL DIGITAL HEALTH MISSION

India launched its National Digital Health Mission in 2020 to develop digital infrastructure for a national digital health ecosystem that can be shared between private and public healthcare providers. Under this scheme, each citizen will be assigned a unique digital ID that contains all their medical records and other health-related data. Challenges in operating such platforms lie in ensuring data and privacy rights, developing the required digital infrastructure, and creating digital literacy among users, among others.

8. ANALYSIS OF TRACING AND TESTING POLICY ACROSS DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

This section seeks to analyse the tracing and testing policy across different countries. The analysis presented operates under several constraints, given the paucity of historical data pertaining to the pandemic and limitations of the data currently available. The charts serve to present an overview of tracing and testing policies. Given the absence of precise data, we use several other factors as proxies to estimate the impact of government response on tracing and testing.

The metrics used to assess the spread and severity of the outbreak are listed below. The indicators below are studied vis-à-vis the testing, tracing and stringent measure adopted by governments:

- **Case fatality ratio (CFR)** is the proportion of individuals diagnosed with a disease who die from that disease and is, therefore, a measure of severity. CFR in this study has been used as a proxy for the fatality of the outbreak, to ascertain the utility of public health measures such as tracing and testing.

It is calculated as follows

$$\text{CFR} = \frac{\text{Number of Deaths from COVID19}}{\text{Number of confirmed cases}}$$

- **The positive rate** indicates the share of tests returning a positive result. It is a proxy for the level of testing relative to the size of the outbreak. According to WHO, a positive rate of less than 5% is an indicator that the epidemic is under control in a country. A high positive rate indicates that the number of confirmed cases is likely to represent only a small fraction of the actual number of infections. A rising positive rate suggests that the virus is spreading faster than the growth seen in confirmed cases. It is calculated as follows

$$\text{Positive rate} = \frac{\text{number of confirmed cases of COVID19}}{\text{Number of people tested}}$$

- **Government Stringency Index** contains the following metrics school closures; workplace closures; cancellation of public events; restrictions on public gatherings; closures of public transport; stay-at-home requirements; public information campaigns; restrictions on internal movements; international travel controls; testing policy; and extent of contact tracing. A higher score indicates a stricter government response (i.e. 100 = strictest response).
- **Reproduction number, R_0** , is the average number of people who will contract a contagious disease from another person with that disease. R_0 helps predict possibilities for the potential transmission or decline of disease. An R_0 less than one indicates that each existing infection causes less than one new infection. Thus implying, that the disease will decline and eventually die out. An R_0 equal to 1, suggests that each existing infection causes one new infection. The disease will stay alive and stable, but there will not be an outbreak or an epidemic. An R_0 greater than one means each existing infection causes more than one new infection. Hence there may be an outbreak or an epidemic.
- **Doubling time** is the number of days required for the number of cases in an epidemic to double.
- **Tests per confirmed cases** is the number of tests a country does to find one Covid19 cases. Countries with few tests per confirmed case do not test widely enough to find all cases.

For the country-wise analysis of tracing and tracking practices, the charts below describe the trends in tracing and testing policy against positive rate and tests per confirmed case. The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time.

8.1 INDIA

The tracing policy for Covid-19 in India from March 2020 has remained consistently comprehensive. Despite fewer reported daily cases between April and May, the stringency index remained at its peak. The robust tracing policy, coupled with an increase in daily testing to compensate for the decline in stringency between August to September, are noteworthy aspects.

The chart below describes the trends in tracing policy and stringency index (secondary axis) against daily cases and daily tests (primary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time.

The chart below describes the trends in testing policy and stringency index (primary axis) against daily cases and daily tests (secondary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time. The graph shows an increase in daily tests as the government adopts an open testing policy. However, the number of daily cases does not see a corresponding rise as one would expect. In around mid-June, India reverted to testing only for those showing symptoms of Covid-19, but daily tests increased in a larger proportion.

The chart below describes the trends in tracing and testing policy and reproduction number (R_0) (secondary axis) against stringency index and doubling time (primary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time. The chart highlights that the doubling rate increases even with the policy of open testing and higher stringency in April. Between June and July, we see a stagnation in doubling time, even though the government started to test only for those showing symptoms of Covid-19 and stringency also was relaxed. Doubling, thus, appears independent of stringency measures, and the tracing and testing policy adopted by India. As India shifted from testing only the symptomatic and key groups to open testing in April, there was a decline in R_0 . After peaking in February, R_0 has shown consistent decline, possibly with the increased stringency measures. R_0 fell below 1 towards September despite the shift in testing only those showing symptoms of Covid-19 and relaxation of stringency measures.

In the chart below, the trends in tracing and testing policy (primary axis) are plotted against case fatality ratio and tests per confirmed cases (secondary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time. As per the data on the tracing policy adopted by India, India shifted from limited to comprehensive tracing in the end of January 2020. Initially, India had a policy of testing those with symptoms and critical groups. By the end of March, the government allowed an open testing policy with the growing severity of the pandemic. The testing policy then reverted to testing only for those only showing symptoms in June 2020. Despite the robust testing and tracing policy, tests per confirmed cases seemed to decline between April and June. The period also saw a dip in case fatality ratio for a brief period after the shift in tracing practices.

In the chart below, the trends in tracing and testing policy (primary axis) are plotted against stringency index and tests per confirmed cases (secondary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time. The rise in stringency by the government post-march, is also visible in the shift in both the testing and tracing policy. The stringency response stagnated over time, as did the tracing and testing policy. Tests per confirmed cases reflect the number of tests a country does to find one Covid-19 case. Fewer tests indicate the country is not testing widely to find all cases. The tests per confirmed cases have largely remained unchanged with the increase in stringency regulation or robust tracing.

Moreover, the shift towards the comprehensive testing did not raise tests per confirmed cases but caused a marginal drop.

In the chart below, the trends in tracing, testing policy and positive rate (primary axis) are plotted against tests per confirmed cases (secondary axis). The policy outcome and severity of the disease are described as a function of time. In India, the positive rate sees a progressive rise with a shift in testing policy to open testing between April and June. Since the tests per confirmed cases declined during this period, the impact of testing and tracing becomes harder to conclude.

TESTING POLICY

0. No testing policy
1. Testing only for those who both (a) have symptoms AND (b) meet specific criteria
2. Testing of anyone showing COVID-19 symptoms
3. Open public testing

TRACING POLICY

0. No Tracing
1. Limited Tracing
2. Comprehensive Testing

8.1.1 How the States Fared in Contact Tracing

Telangana tested only 14 contacts per Covid-19 confirmed case, making it a state where 'less than 50th percentile of contacts tested'. In the state, authorities traced less than half of all persons the Covid-19 patient came in contact with. None of the other south Indian states performed this low on tracing. The Telangana government used geolocation technology to track over 25,000 people under home-quarantine using a Covid-19 monitoring system, as early as April. The TSCop, an app developed by the Telangana police, was deployed to mark houses of foreign returnees.

In Karnataka, contact tracing capacity dropped from 47 per patient in June to less than 6 primary contacts per patient in July. The contact tracing data from July 26 to August 5 shows Bengaluru Rural traced only with 1.57 contacts per patient. In Bengaluru Urban, about 4.4 contacts were traced per patient. Karnataka government developed eight in-house apps to manage the tracing and tracking aspects of the pandemic (Bharadwaj, 2020). The contact tracing exercise in the state involved checking in with patients at multiple points to reduce errors and increased compliance with state quarantine measures. Karnataka also conducted a household survey to identify the elderly, pregnant and the comorbid population. These people were regularly contacted through the Apthamitra teleconsultation helpline and the local health officers and ASHAs, who reviewed their health and connected them with health resources for both Covid-19 and non-COVID illnesses. Over 10,000 government personnel were employed as contact tracers in Karnataka (Government of Karnataka, 2021).

Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu both introduced disease surveillance and contact tracing early on in the pandemic. Procedures such as syndromic surveillance and testing for all individuals seeking care for severe acute respiratory illness or influenza-like illness at health care facilities; demarcation of 5-km containment zones surrounding cases for daily house-to-house surveillance; daily follow-up of all contacts of laboratory-confirmed or suspected Covid-19 cases to test these individuals 5 to 14 days after their contact with a primary case. Contact-tracing efforts in the states reached 3,084,885 known exposed contacts of confirmed cases by August 1 2020 (ICMR COVID Study Group, COVID Epidemiology & Data Management Team, COVID Laboratory Team, VRDLN Team, 2020). Andhra Pradesh tested 54 contacts per confirmed case and was categorised as the state with '50-75th percentile of contacts tested'; Tamil Nadu (44), Kerala (40) and Karnataka (93) have been labelled as states with 'more than 75th percentile of contacts tested' (Nilesh, 2020).

In Bhilwara, Rajasthan, the administration set up 2,000 contact-tracing teams. Their model engaged ASHA workers, village elders and panchayat leader and grassroots health workers, thereby screening roughly 92% of the population within nine days.

The Himachal Pradesh government assigned block officers, gram panchayat officials and district magistrates as nodal officers, designating them responsible for their respective areas of jurisdiction. Around 16,000 employees screened the entire population of 68 lakh.

The government paid particular attention to its residents stranded outside the state borders. Every single returnee was registered and followed up to check for signs or symptoms of the disease. Corona Mukht Himachal App tracked the user's location using GPS technology and if found to violate home quarantine rules, the user was sent to institutional quarantine.

In Punjab, the disease was spread mainly by people coming from foreign countries who had landed at Indira Gandhi International Airport. The information on these travellers reached the Punjab headquarters after a delay of 4-5 days. Mumbai has been unable to contact trace effectively due to the high population density in its chawls.

Uttar Pradesh also failed to trace and track international travellers as well as domestic travellers who were employed as labourers in other states (Puntambekar, Sharma, & Mulchandani, 2020). Several states such as Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana and Tamil Nadu have used call detail records for tracing contacts of Covid positive patients.

8.1.2. How India Compares With Other Countries on Tracing Policy and Privacy Protection

Comparitech assessed privacy protection and the state of surveillance in 47 countries to see where governments are failing to protect the privacy and/or are creating surveillance states. The index covers aspects such as Statutory Protection, Privacy Enforcement, Identity Cards and Biometrics, Data-sharing, Visual Surveillance Communication, Interception, Workplace Monitoring, Government Access to Data Communication, Data Retention, Surveillance of Medical, Financial and Movement, Border and Trans-Border Issues, Leadership and Democratic Safeguards.

In the chart below, the trends in tracing and privacy protection are plotted for a select batch of countries. The score card represents the country's commitment and efforts towards protecting individual freedom and respect for privacy. The tracing policy adopted by each country is also marked in the graph.

Scoring system

4.1-5.0 = Upholding privacy standards on a consistent basis

3.6-4.0 = Significant safeguards and protections

3.1-3.5 = Adequate safeguards against abuse

2.6-3.0 = Some safeguards but weakened protections

2.1-2.5 = Systemic failure to maintain safeguards

1.6-2.0 = Extensive surveillance

1.1-1.5 = Endemic surveillance

India scored 2.4 on this index, indicating the systemic failure to maintain safeguards. However, it adopted comprehensive tracing as a strategy to contain the spread of the outbreak. India fared particularly low on measures such as statutory protections and privacy enforcement. China, a country which was marked as a country in endemic surveillance, also adopted a strict tracing policy. As did Russia, despite the poor performance on privacy protection.

8.2 SINGAPORE

Singapore launched its TraceTogether app in March 2020 to augment its ongoing contact tracing measures. One of the first contact tracing apps to be used during the pandemic, it had registered as many as 2,70,000 users as of November 2020 with a penetration of about 48% of its population. The app uses Bluetooth connection for proximity tracking between users. Users exchange anonymised IDs, which are then stored in an encrypted form, only on the user phone through cryptographic techniques. The anonymized IDs are refreshed every 15 minutes (R Gupta et al, 2020).

Post April 2020, Singapore limited testing to those with symptoms in the key groups. Government stringency level dropped drastically by almost 50% in June, when compared to the level in April. Tests per confirmed cases increase considerably after August and may have offset the low levels of stringency. In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases have been plotted on the secondary axis. The stringency index, testing policy and tracing policy have been plotted on the primary axis.

In the chart below, stringency index has been placed on the secondary axis, while all other variables remain on the primary axis. Despite the stringent measures and consistent robust testing and tracing, we see a peak in positive rate between April-May. However, Singapore has had rapidly-declining levels of positive rates thereon.

8.3 VIETNAM

Vietnam has been lauded for its Covid-19 response; which focussed on strategic testing, digitally-aided contact tracing, effective and transparent public communication, citizen participation and general preparedness gained from their experience with SARS a few years ago. The lessons learned from Vietnam are that a pandemic like Covid-19 can be tackled only through aggressive testing, strict self-isolation and community participation in physical distancing measures.

Vietnam launched its proximity tracing app Bluezone in April. The app uses Bluetooth to detect smartphones that come within about 6.5 feet of each other. The time and duration of the contact is also captured. The app claims it does not collect data on users' locations and that the collected information is anonymised, with only competent health authorities allowed to identify those who are infected and their primary and secondary contacts (Umeda, 2020). According to reports in the state media, the app has been downloaded more than 20 million times and has successfully traced 1,400 suspected cases (Kim, 2020).

Vietnam adopted the policy of comprehensive tracing right from March 2020. In April 2020, the government implemented stricter measures and moved towards an open testing policy. Between April and May, tests per confirmed cases increased to probably offset the decline in stringency level. This strategy is visible again between June and September, where stringency level is further reduced, and tests per confirmed cases is increased. Vietnam managed to contain positive rates to very low values (Thuy, 2020).

In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases have been plotted on the secondary axis. The stringency index, the testing policy and tracing policy have been plotted on the primary axis.

The stringency index and positive rate have been placed on the secondary axis in the chart below, while all other variables remain on the primary axis.

The stringency index and positive rate have been placed on the secondary axis in the chart below, while all other variables remain on the primary axis.

8.4 THAILAND

Thailand is using a combination of contact tracing and symptom reporting applications for contact tracing such as DDC-Care (symptom-reporting), AOT Airport Application (for tracking travel history), and Morchana Application (contact tracing). As many as 600,000 citizens have downloaded the app for use as of November 2020. Concerns have been raised over the possible repurposing of the large amounts of data captured.

Thailand escalated its stringency response late March 2020. However, the country adopted a comprehensive tracing response mid-April and it continued to test only those showing symptoms of Covid-19. Thailand's positive rate also seems to have flat-lined after peaking in April. But it remained well above 1. Thailand increased its tests per confirmed cases during the period of stringent measures. In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases are plotted on the primary axis, while testing and tracing policy are placed on the primary axis.

The graph below depicts the stringency index on the primary axis. Positive rate, testing and tracking policy are plotted on the secondary axis.

8.5 SOUTH KOREA

South Korea’s widespread digital contact tracing efforts have been helpful in breaking the chain of transmission of Covid-19. Besides building a centralised system that routinely monitors people’s movements, contact tracers themselves are given access to various sources of data; including footage from security cameras, mobile base station data, and credit card transaction data for

early detection of emerging hotspots and timely identification of contacts. The contact tracing data is routinely put out, raising serious privacy concerns. However, culturally and legally, the country is more open to sharing personal data, which is why technological solutions could be scaled up effectively. As early as January, South Korea adopted comprehensive tracing and an open testing policy. South Korea also had peaked its tests per confirmed cases and was testing widely. It raised its stringency index only in March, and lowered its stringency index to 50% after April. It managed to iron out its positive rate with its shift in policy towards robust tracing and testing as well as well-timed stringent response.

In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases are plotted on the primary axis, while testing, tracing and stringency policy are measured on the secondary axis.

The graph above depicts the stringency index on the primary axis. Positive rate, testing and tracking policy are plotted on the secondary axis.

8.6 UNITED KINGDOM

The National Health Service (NHS) launched a contact-tracing smartphone app for people living in England and Wales that uses decentralised “exposure notification” and “exposure logging” technology developed by Apple and Google in September. It seeks to notify people when they have been exposed and allow symptom reporting, among other functions. Scotland and Northern Ireland have launched their own apps.

United Kingdom remained consistently high on the stringency index throughout the period. It moved to testing for those with covid19 symptoms only in May. Prior to that, the country tested for only those from key groups showing symptoms. UK shifted to a comprehensive testing policy in June. It managed to iron out its positive rate up until October. October saw a slight spike in positive rate and also a shift to limited tracing policy. UK expanded the coverage of its tests only in September. In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases and stringency index are plotted on the primary axis, while testing and tracing policy are measured on the secondary axis.

The graph below depicts the stringency index on the primary axis. Positive rate, testing and tracking policy are plotted on the secondary axis.

8.7 UNITED STATES

In the United States, there has been minimal state-level efforts taken on tracing. As many as 19 states are using contact tracing apps and several others are in pilot phase or exploring the option. However, only a few states openly report contact-tracing metrics. Several states are using the system designed by Google and Apple.

The United States remained consistently stringent throughout the period. It adopted an open testing policy, however stuck to a limited testing protocol. The USA had extremely low tests per confirmed cases. In the chart below, tests per confirmed cases and stringency index are plotted on the primary axis, while testing and tracing policy are measured on the secondary axis.

The graph below depicts the stringency index on the primary axis. Positive rate, testing and tracing policy are plotted on the secondary axis.

8.8 Comparison of Digital Contact Tracing Models

COUNTRY	SINGAPORE	SOUTH KOREA
APPROACH	Hybrid model – Decentralised contact logging and centralised contact tracing & follow-up	Centralised model; contact tracers themselves are given access to various sources of data, including footage from security cameras, mobile base station data, and credit card transaction data
DATA COLLECTION AND DATA STORAGE	All data collected is stored locally on the user’s phone and encrypted	Centralised system that collects and analyses different kinds of data
PRIVACY RIGHT	It does not store information about where the contact happened. No data is uploaded to the government. The government will then request for him/her to upload the data to facilitate contact tracing of his/her close contacts.	Publicly shares patients’ contact-trace data-including pseudonymised information on demographics, infection information, and travel logs
CONTACT TRACING MODEL	Proximity tracking and digital check-ins	Facility visits, including pharmacies and medical facilities; cellular GPS data from cell phones; credit card transaction logs; closed-circuit television. This information was combined with interviews and cross-checked with other data to identify contacts and take appropriate containment measures.
APP	TraceTogether	

COUNTRY	UNITED KINGDOM	THAILAND
APPROACH	Decentralised “exposure notification” and “exposure logging” technology developed by Apple and Google.	Decentralised model
DATA COLLECTION AND DATA STORAGE	Diagnosis keys are retained on the user’s mobile device for 14 days. Submitted diagnosis keys are retained on the UK Department of Health and Social Care secure computing infrastructure for 14 days. QR codes that are scanned by the user when visiting venues are deleted after 21 days	All data collected is stored and displayed in an anonymous form. Users will be asked to share these records only when contacted by the authorities as part of contact tracing investigations.
PRIVACY RIGHT	NHS states that data will only ever be used for NHS care, management, evaluation and research.	The Personal Data Protection Act B.E. 2562 (2019) (PDPA) effective from May 2020.
CONTACT TRACING MODEL	Proximity tracking and digital check-ins	Contact tracing applications used together with the cell phone location data of the user
APP	NHS COVID-19	MorChana

COUNTRY	VIETNAM
APPROACH	Decentralised model
DATA COLLECTION AND DATA STORAGE	The app claims it does not collect data on users' locations and that the collected information is anonymised, with only competent health authorities allowed to identify those who are infected and their primary and secondary contacts.
PRIVACY RIGHT	Vietnam lacks a robust legal framework to regulate data privacy and ethical use of data
CONTACT TRACING MODEL	Bluetooth
APP	Bluezone

9. PRINCIPLES FOR A TECHNOLOGY-AIDED MODEL FOR TRACING AND TRACKING COVID-19 IN INDIA

9.1 Policy Considerations

The public health response to the Covid-19 outbreak in India has been enforced in a top-down manner and did not evolve as an intervention at the community level early on. Public trust is essential for successful interventions. In many ways, public health communication around the disease was not effective enough to encourage self-reporting. Moreover, in the absence of such communication, the importance of individual responsibility in disease control was not emphasised enough.

Instances where the personal data of those who had tested positive were made public and selective targeting of communities during the outbreak of the pandemic led to widespread erosion of trust in tracing measures (Mounika, 2020), (Thappar and Wahidi, 2020). Public health experts feel an enforcement-oriented approach to handling the pandemic that involved barricading entrances to homes and hyperlocal lockdowns instilled fear in the public and discouraged people from reporting symptoms on the Aarogya Setu app.

There should be a clear division of responsibilities on disease surveillance and response measures between state and central governments. Such distinctions must also be outlined vis-à-vis the roles played by the Indian Council for Medical Research (ICMR), National Disease Control Centre (NCDC) and Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) during public health emergencies like Covid-19.

9.2 Combination of manual and digital contact tracing interventions

What would be more effective in a nation like India is a combination of physical and digital tracing and tracking methods. This should be done taking into consideration that only 50% of the population the country currently has access to the internet. Now that Covid-19 has spread to rural and peri-urban areas where internet access is poor, person-to-person surveillance measures must continue in earnest as well. Telehealth can go a long way in ensuring coverage of those excluded due to the digital divide.

Considering that the WHO benchmark for successful Covid-19 contact-tracing is to trace and quarantine 80% of close contacts within three days of a case being confirmed, contact tracing must be carried out in a timely manner, while capturing data on primary and secondary levels of contact as well (Lewis, 2020). With sufficient training, women self-help groups and ASHA workers can play a large role in collecting valuable data at the grassroots levels. Household tracing instead of individual tracing may help ensure better coverage of children.

Some states already maintain comprehensive e-health records, especially in the southern parts of the country. The Covid-19 pandemic should provide the necessary impetus for other states to follow suit on this front. Data on co-morbidity should be also be collected and analysed as nearly three in four Covid-19 patients have co-morbidities, according to data put out by the IDSP. In this manner, vulnerable groups can be identified to develop effective vaccination plans.

The ideal digital technology-aided model for pandemic response would also combine tools used for epidemiological surveillance, early and timely detection, interruption of chain of disease transmission, long-term follow-ups and communication of healthcare information to public.

These are the basic principles that such a model that combines the use of traditional and digital technology can follow for tracking and tracing:

Public benefit

Developers and policymakers must ensure public benefit outweighs the risks associated with deploying any digital technology for tracking or tracing Covid-19.

Garnering public trust

Public messaging by political leaders, health authorities, media and others on disease control measures should be congruent and unified, especially to gain public trust and ensure voluntary use of digital health tools. Regular communication and realistic offers of support will help ensure quarantine compliance and motivate individuals to be responsible about reporting suspected symptoms (Woolliscroft, Shaif, Jackson, Pagden, Redgrave and Heller, 2020).

Ensuring efficacy and scientific validity

Considering there is not enough consensus among members of the scientific community about the efficacy of digital technology for tracking and tracing, the pandemic should not be a reason to lower scientific standards. Validation tests and protocol must be developed to assess the efficacy and accuracy of the technology in use.

Time limit

All measures taken for heightened surveillance using digital health technology should have an expiration date. Users must be informed of the reason and duration for which data is collected.

Privacy Protection

Spatial proximity tracking tools among phone users are, all other things being equal, less privacy-invasive than personal contact tracing or quarantine enforcement apps. Tools using aggregate mobile phone tower data are, on average, less privacy-invasive compared with tools based on Global Positioning System data and sensor tracking for individual users.

Preserving autonomy

Personal autonomy must be preserved. The use of such applications and tools must be personally-motivated choices made by the user and should not be enforced or mandated at any level. Moreover, data handling practices must ensure personal autonomy of the users in how the data is being shared and stored.

Avoiding Discrimination

Digital tracing and tracking tools carry an inherent risk of discrimination. Safeguards must be put in place to ensure the large amounts of health and demographic data collected through these apps and tools are not used to further stigmatise underserved populations. Instead, such data should be contextualised and utilised for evidence-based action to bridge persistent health inequities.

Preventing Repurposing

There is an overarching risk of data collected by digital health tools being repurposed for commercial gains and other forms of surveillance in the absence of robust safeguards against third-party sharing.

Avoiding digital inequality

Considering that only one-third of the world's population had access to a smartphone in 2019, and the same proportion lacked access to any mobile phone, digital health technology used during the pandemic must not exclude marginalised communities and deepen health inequities. For this, digital tracing and tracking efforts must be carried out alongside traditional interventions such as door-to-door, telehealth and other in-person monitoring measures.

Investment in contact tracing

Studies suggest that incremental increases in levels of contact tracing are likely to bring in diminishing benefits in disease control (Armbruster and Brandeau, 2007). Simulation models and cost-effectiveness analysis can be used to determine the optimal level of investment in contact tracing.

Role of the Private Sector

Technology companies should become long-term partners in pandemic preparedness, and not just during public health emergencies. (Budd, J., Miller, B.S., Manning, E.M. et al, 2020). Technology and telecommunication companies could be called upon to share data they have in a 'proportionate, ethical and privacy-preserving' manner as well. The private healthcare sector can play a large role in ensuring tracing and testing measures do not run into roadblocks and are not used to create distrust and stigma against those testing positive. Industry representatives have spoken about the need to treat the private healthcare sector with less suspicion to incentivise their participation in Covid-19 response measures.

10. WAY FORWARD: ROLE OF IOT, BIG DATA ANALYTICS, AI AND BLOCK CHAIN TECHNOLOGY

The internet of things (IoT), big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), and blockchain technology can help create an interrelated digital eco-system for better provision of healthcare. Data can be collected and updated real-time at scale if IoT is adopted in hospital and clinical settings.

Using big data analytics, the collected data can be used to understand trends in the disease and predict future outcomes to aid informed policymaking. AI and deep learning can enhance detection and diagnoses of the patients in a timely and cost-effective manner. Blockchain technology will help ensure the security and traceability of the data (Ting, Carin, Dzau et al, 2020).

INTER-RELATED DIGITAL ECO-SYSTEM

1. **Internet of Things (IoT)** – Platform for public health agencies to access data for monitoring Covid-19.
2. **Big Data Analytics** - For modelling studies of viral activity that can inform decisionmakers and ensure effectiveness of interventions.
3. **Social media and communication applications** – For better and targeted public health education and communication.
4. **AI and deep learning** - For rapid detection and diagnosis of Covid -19 cases using AI algorithms as initial screening tools. AI algorithms can also be effectively used to triage cases. However, such algorithms require training with data sets and the projections must be evaluated for accuracy.
5. **Blockchain technology** - Ensures a system of copying data in multiple physical locations across an integrated peer-to-peer network with a back-linked database and cryptographic protocol. This ensures the data is secure but traceable.

11. VACCINE DELIVERY – THE PRIORITY LIST

The COVID vaccine is here, despite all the scepticism on its efficacy and the way the approvals were speeded up. As the country gets ready to vaccinate its population, the major question that arises is on who gets it first and how does the 70 per cent of total population get inoculated to complete the entire process. States with high vulnerability would stake their claim to the vaccine first, while states where prevalence is high would want the same. Urban India would debate that villages have not been impacted and can be tackled later. The prioritization is not going to be easy.

Using tracking and tracing data, the priority can indeed be made in a scientific manner based on evidence. Data would help us identify the spread of the diseases and allow us to identify where the virus would travel next. It would also show what populations are more prone to catch the virus and which sections of society need to be addressed first.

While the worldwide evidence suggests that those above 70 are the most vulnerable, in India it is those below 60 who have contributed to more than 50 percent deaths. And while across the western world the poorer sections of society and the minorities have been badly impacted, in India the numbers show quite the opposite tendency.

The east was relatively better off. Maharashtra, Kerala, and Gujarat saw a huge upsurge in cases that continued well beyond the April to June quarter. These states remain vulnerable. On the eastern coast, Andhra Pradesh was a leader for quite a while and, therefore, would be top contenders for the vaccines. Among the frontline workers, policemen and health care workers will remain at risk and need the vaccine quickly. The data will tell us who among these two groups is more vulnerable. If educational institutions are to be opened up, then teachers and the non-teaching staff will need to be immunised before schools and colleges reopen.

The point is that tracking and tracing must continue on a war footing. Else, we would not be able to identify and register those who need the vaccine the most. Those who are enthusiastic about the Aadhar route fail to note this point. Those registered on UIDAI might not be the most vulnerable. Those who haven't been registered might need it first.

REFERENCES

1. Agrawal, R. (2020, August 05). Are contact-tracing apps helping tame the pandemic? Mint. <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/are-contact-tracing-apps-helping-tame-the-pandemic-11596611635201.html>
2. Armbruster, B., Brandeau, M.L. (2007). Contact tracing to control infectious disease: when enough is enough. *Health Care Management Science*, 10, 341–355. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10729-007-9027-6>
3. Banerjee, P. (2020, November 24). Experts seek full Aarogya Setu code, not bits of it. Mint. Retrieved from: <https://www.livemint.com/technology/tech-news/experts-seek-full-aarogya-setu-code-not-bits-of-it-11606178251490.html>
4. Bharadwaj, S. (2020, August 7). Superspreading' Caused Most COVID-19 Transmission In Karnataka, Contact Tracing Data Show. IndiaSpend. Retrieved from: <https://www.indiaspend.com/superspreading-caused-most-covid-19-transmission-in-karnataka-contact-tracing-data-show/>
5. Braithwaite, I., Callender, T., Bullock, M., Aldridge, R.W. (2020). Automated and partly automated contact tracing: a systematic review to inform the control of COVID-19. *Lancet Digital Health* 2020; 2: e607–21. Retrieved from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(20\)30184-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30184-9)
6. Budd, J., Miller, B.S., Manning, E.M. et al. (2020). Digital technologies in the public-health response to COVID-19. *Nature Medicine*, 26, 1183–1192. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-1011-4>
7. Criddle, C. & Kelion, L. (2020, May 07). Coronavirus contact-tracing: World split between two types of app. BBC News. Retrieved from: <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-52355028>
8. Gasser, U., Ienca, M., Scheibner, J., Sleight, J., & Vayena, E. (2020). *Lancet Digital Health* 2020, 2, e425–34. Retrieved from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(20\)30137-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30137-0)
9. Government of India. (2020). Key Indicators (22 States and UTs from Phase 1) – National Family Health Survey 5 2019-20. International Institute for Population Sciences: New Delhi. Retrieved from: http://rchiips.org/nfhs/factsheet_NFHS-5.shtml
10. Government of Karnataka. (2021). Covid-19 Karnataka Dashboard. Covid-19 Information Portal. Retrieved from: <https://covid19.karnataka.gov.in/covid-dashboard/dashboard.html>
11. Government of Kerala. (2020). Covid brigade report. Covid19 Jagratha. Retrieved from: <https://covid19jagratha.kerala.nic.in/home/addBrigadeDashBoard>
12. Grimwood-Taylor, L. (2020, May 13). Contact Tracing Apps: Differing Global Approaches. A Blog by Baker McKenzie. Retrieved from: <https://www.connectontech.com/2020/05/13/contact-tracing-apps-differing-global-approaches/>

13. Gupta, R., Bedi, M., Goyal, P., Wadhera, S. and Verma, V. (2020). Analysis of COVID-19 Tracking Tool in India: Case Study of Aarogya Setu Mobile Application. *Digital Government: Research & Practice*. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3416088>
14. Hart, V., Siddhart, D., Cantrell, B., Tretikov, L., Eckersley, P., Langford, J., Leibrand, S., Kakade, S., Latta, S., Lewis, D., Tessaro, S. & Weyl, G. (2020). Outpacing the virus: Digital response to containing the spread of COVID-19 while mitigating privacy risks. (COVID-19 Rapid Response Impact Initiative | White Paper 5). Edmond J. Safra Center for Ethics. Retrieved from: https://ethics.harvard.edu/files/center-for-ethics/files/white_paper_5_outpacing_the_virus_final.pdf?m=1586179217
15. ICMR COVID Study Group, COVID Epidemiology & Data Management Team, COVID Laboratory Team, VRDLN Team. (2020). Laboratory surveillance for SARS-CoV-2 in India: Performance of testing & descriptive epidemiology of detected COVID-19. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 151:424-37.
16. Johari, A. (2020, November 17). Aarogya Setu: Has the world's most downloaded contact-tracing app actually been effective? Scroll. Retrieved from: <https://scroll.in/article/978309/aarogya-setu-has-the-worlds-most-downloaded-contact-tracing-app-actually-been-effective>
17. Joshi, D. and Kak, A. (2020, April 19). India's digital response to COVID-19 risks inefficacy, exclusion and discrimination. *The Caravan*. Retrieved from: <https://caravanmagazine.in/health/india-digital-response-covid-19-risks-inefficacy-exclusion-discrimination>
18. Kim, S. (2020, September 29). Vietnam's contact-tracing app: Public health tool or creeping surveillance? *South East Asia Globe*. Retrieved from: <https://southeastasiaglobe.com/bluezone-contact-tracing-app/>
19. Kim, N. (2020, March 06). 'More scary than coronavirus': South Korea's health alerts expose private lives. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/mar/06/more-scary-than-coronavirus-south-koreas-health-alerts-expose-private-lives>
20. Kretzschmar, M.E., Rozhnova, R. Bootsma, M.C.J., van Boven, M., van de Wijgert, J.H.H.M, Bonten, M.J.M. Impact of delays on effectiveness of contact tracing strategies for COVID-19: a modelling study. *Lancet Public Health* 2020; 5: e452–59 Retrieved from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(20\)30157-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(20)30157-2)
21. Kucharski, A. J., Klepac, P., Conlan, A., Kissler, S. M., Tang, M. L., Fry, H., Gog, J. R., Edmunds, W. J., & CMMID COVID-19 working group (2020). Effectiveness of isolation, testing, contact tracing, and physical distancing on reducing transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in different settings: a mathematical modelling study. *The Lancet. Infectious diseases*, 20(10), 1151–1160. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30457-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30457-6)
22. Lewis, D. (2020). Why many countries failed at COVID contact-tracing - but some got it right. *Nature*, 588, 384-387. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-03518-4>

23. Mehrotra, K. (2020, April 11). Behind Aarogya Setu app push: 'At least 50% people must download for impact'. The Indian Express. Retrieved from: <https://indianexpress.com/article/coronavirus/behind-aarogya-setu-app-push-at-least-50-people-must-download-for-impact-6357121/>
24. Mihindukulasuriya, R. (2020, June 13). India has at least 62 apps to deal with Covid, but they all do the same job mostly. The Print. Retrieved from: <https://theprint.in/india/india-has-at-least-62-apps-to-deal-with-covid-but-they-all-do-the-same-job-mostly/439040/>
25. Morley, J., Cowls, J. Taddeo, M. & Floridi, L. (2020). Ethical guidelines for COVID-19 tracing apps. *Nature*, 582, 29-31. Retrieved from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-01578-0>
26. Nilesh, V. (2020, June 04). New ICMR data raises questions over Telangana's contact tracing efforts. The New Indian Express. Retrieved from: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/telangana/2020/jun/04/new-icmr-data-raises-questions-over-telanganas-contact-tracing-efforts-2152085.html>
27. Norton Rose Fulbright. (2020). Contact tracing apps: A new world for data privacy. Publication. Retrieved from: <https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en-in/knowledge/publications/d7a9a296/contact-tracing-apps-a-new-world-for-data-privacy>
28. O'Neill, P.H., Ryan-Mosley, T. Johnson, B. (2020, May 07). A flood of coronavirus apps are tracking us. Now it's time to keep track of them. MIT Technology Review. Retrieved from: <https://www.technologyreview.com/2020/05/07/1000961/launching-mittr-covid-tracing-tracker/>
29. Puntambekar, V., Sharma, P., & Mulchandani, M. (2020). Contact tracing: a global perspective and recommendations for the. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 3740-3745.
30. Rajeevan, R. (2020, March 26). 'Privacy Not a Concern, Checking Spread of Virus is': K'taka Govt Publishes Details of Foreign Returnees. News 18 India. Retrieved from: <https://www.news18.com/news/india/privacy-not-a-concern-checking-virus-spread-is-ktaka-govt-publishes-details-of-foreign-returnees-2550835.html>
31. Roser, M., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., and Hasell, J. (2020). Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19). OurWorldInData.org. Retrieved from: <https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>
32. Shashidhar, K.J. (2020). Aarogya Setu App and its many conflicts. Digital Frontier. Retrieved from: <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/aarogya-setu-app-many-conflicts-67442/>
33. Thappar, A. & Wahidi, Z. (2020, August 24). 'Unjust and unfair': What three High Courts said about the arrests of Tablighi Jamaat members. Scroll. Retrieved from: <https://scroll.in/article/971195/unjust-and-unfair-what-three-high-courts-said-about-the-arrests-of-tablighi-jamaat-members>

34. Ting, D.S.W., Carin, L., Dzau, V. et al. (2020). Digital technology and COVID-19. *Nature Medicine*, 26, 459–461. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0824-5>
35. Thuy, T.L. (2020, October 20). Vietnam is fighting Covid without pitting economic growth against public health. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2020/oct/20/vietnam-covid-economic-growth-public-health-coronavirus>
36. Umeda, S. (2020, October 30). Vietnam: Foreign Nationals on Short-Term Visits Required to Use Contact Tracing App during Their Stay in Vietnam. *Global Legal Monitor*. Retrieved from: <https://www.loc.gov/law/foreign-news/article/vietnam-foreign-nationals-on-short-term-visits-required-to-use-contact-tracing-app-during-their-stay-in-vietnam/>
37. Whitelaw, S., Mamas, M.A., Topol, E. and Van Spall, H.G.C. (2020). Applications of digital technology in COVID-19 pandemic planning and response. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 2(8), e435-e440. Retrieved from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500\(20\)30142-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2589-7500(20)30142-4).
38. Woolliscroft, T., Shaif, A., Jackson, A., Pagden, S., Redgrave, P. Heller, T. (2020). Best practice in contact tracing: How should an effective system be organised? *TheBMJOpinion*. Retrieved from: <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2020/09/08/best-practice-in-contact-tracing-how-should-an-effective-system-be-organised/>
39. World Health Organization. (2017). Contact Tracing. Q&A Detail. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/q-a-detail/contact-tracing>
40. World Health Organization. (2020). Ethical considerations to guide the use of digital proximity tracking technologies for COVID-19 contact tracing. Interim Guidance. Retrieved from: https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-Ethics_Contact_tracing_apps-2020.1

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1. G. Sudhir is a former IAS officer. He was Chairman of the Commission of Inquiry to study the Socio-economic and Educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.
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3. Neelima Khetan headed the CSR division for companies like Coca-Cola, the Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc Limited. She is now visiting fellow at Brookings India.
4. Amitabh Kundu has been chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by Ministry of Minority Affairs. Currently, he is chairs a Committee for Swachh Bharat Mission at the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation.
5. Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with more than three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing, and retail businesses.
6. Saleema Razvi is a Research Economist at the Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously served in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, Population Foundation of India, and UNICEF.
7. Abdul Shaban is a Professor at Tata Institute of Social Sciences. He has been a member of Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee, Chief Minister's High-Powered Committee on Muslims, Government of Maharashtra; and Sudhir Commission, Telangana.
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